

**UNIVERSITY
OF EAST
SARAJEVO**

**FACULTY OF
TECHNOLOGY
ZVORNIK**

W W T T T I N T E R N A T I O N A L C O N G R E S S

**ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENT AND MATERIALS
IN PROCESS INDUSTRY
EEM2023**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

**JAHORINA
MARCH 20-23, 2023**

**REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA
BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA**

www.tfzv.ues.rs.ba
www.eem.tfzv.ues.rs.ba

CO-ORGANIZED BY

**FACULTY OF
TECHNOLOGY AND
METALLURGY
Belgrade, Serbia**

**INSTITUTE OF
PHYSICS
Belgrade, Serbia**

**UNION OF ENGINEERS AND
TECHNICIANS OF SERBIA
Belgrade, Serbia**

**FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY
Banja Luka, Bosnia and
Herzegovina**

**FACULTY OF FOOD
TECHNOLOGY
Osijek, Croatia**

UNIVERSITY OF EAST SARAJEVO
FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY ZVORNIK

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

VIII INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS

*ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENT AND MATERIALS IN
PROCESS INDUSTRY*

EEM2023

UNDER THE AUSPICES OF
MINISTRY OF ECONOMY AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP OF THE REPUBLIC OF
SRPSKA

AND

ACADEMY OF SCIENCES AND ARTS OF THE REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA

JAHORINA, MARCH 20-23, 2023
REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA
BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

PUBLISHER

UNIVERSITY OF EAST SARAJEVO

FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY

Karakaj 34a, 75 400 Zvornik

Republic of Srpska, B&H

Phone: +387 56 260 190

e-mail: sekretar@tfzv.ues.rs.ba

web: <https://eem.tfvz.ues.rs.ba/>

FOR PUBLISHER

Dragan Vujadinović, PhD, dean

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Dragan Vujadinović, PhD, chairman | Mirjana Beribaka, PhD, secretary | Vesna Cvijetinović, MA, secretary | Slavko Smiljanić, PhD | Svetlana Peleliš, PhD | Dragica Lazić, PhD | Vladan Mičić, PhD | Dragan Tošković, PhD | Ljubica Vasiljević, PhD | Milenko Smiljanić, PhD | Vaso Novaković, PhD | Zoran Obrenović, PhD | Radislav Filipović, PhD | Novo Škrebić, BSc | Zoran Petković, MSc | Milan Vukić, PhD | Vesna Gojković Cvjetković, PhD | Srdan Vuković, MSc | Danijela Rajić, MSc | Jelena Vulinović, MSc | Nebojša Vasiljević, MSc | Duško Kostić, MSc |

SCIENTIFIC AND PROGRAMME COMMITTEE

Muhammed Ernur Akiner, PhD, *Turkey* | Safia Akram, PhD, *Pakistan* | Sanja Armaković, PhD, *Serbia* | Stevan Armaković, PhD, *Serbia* | Goran Anačkov, PhD, *Serbia* | Jurislav Babić, PhD, *Croatia* | Milica Balaban, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Branko Bugarski, PhD, *Serbia* | Dragica Chamovska, PhD, *North Macedonia* | Rui Costa, PhD, *Portugal* | Victoria Custodis, PhD, *Switzerland* | Vesna Gojković Cvjetković, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | George Dedoussis, PhD, *Greece* | Aleksandar Došić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Mikhail A. Egorov, PhD, *Russia* | Radislav Filipović, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Ilse Fraeye, PhD, *Belgium* | Matteo Gherardi, PhD, *Italy* | Miladin Gligorić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Regina Fuchs-Godec, PhD, *Slovenia* | Dragana Grujić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Aleksandra Jovanović, PhD, *Serbia* | Murat Kaya, PhD, *Turkey* | Dragana Kešelj, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Birol Kılıç, PhD, *Turkey* | Güliden Başığit Kılıç, PhD, *Turkey* | Časlav Lačnjevac, PhD, *Serbia* | Dragica Lazić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Borislav Malinović, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Vladan Mičić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Marija Mitrović, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Ali Reza Nejadmohammad Namaghi, PhD, *Iran* | Vaso Novaković, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Zoran Obrenović, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Božana Odžaković, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Miomir Pavlović, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Darja Pečar, PhD, *Slovenia* | Svetlana Peleliš, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Eva Pellicer, PhD, *Spain* | Mitar Perušić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Zoran Petrović, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Nevena Puač, PhD, *Serbia* | Snežana Radulović, PhD, *Serbia* | Ivan Ristić, PhD, *Serbia* | Andrei Rotaru, PhD, *Romania* | Anastasia Semenova, PhD, *Russia* | Milenko Smiljanić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Slavko Smiljanić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Jordi Sort, PhD, *Spain* | Ana Stojanovic, PhD, *Switzerland* | Srećko Stopić, PhD, *Germany* | Nikola Škoro, PhD, *Serbia* | Goran Tadić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Renjith Thomas, PhD, *India* | Igor Tomašević, PhD, *Serbia* | Milorad Tomić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Vladimir Tomović, PhD, *Serbia* | Dragan Tošković, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Petar Uskoković, PhD, *Serbia* | Ljubica Vasiljević, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Đendi Vaštag, PhD, *Serbia* | Dragan Vujadinović, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Milan Vukić, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* | Darko Vuksanović, PhD, *Montenegro* | Magdalena Parlinska-Wojtan, PhD, *Poland* | Rafael Zambelli, PhD, *Brazil* | Sanja Oručević-Žuljević, PhD, *Bosnia and Herzegovina* |

EDITORIAL BOARD

Dragan Vujadinović, PhD
Mirjana Beribaka, PhD

TECHNICAL EDITORS

Srdan Vuković, MSc
Danijela Rajić, MSc

PROOFREADER

Vesna Cvijetinović, MA

DOMAIN

ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENT AND MATERIALS IN PROCESS INDUSTRY

PUBLISHED: 2023

ISBN: 978-99955-81-44-2

The authors have full responsibility for the originality and content of their own papers.

UV-FILTERS BENZOPHENONES AS LIGANDS FOR ANDROGEN RECEPTORS- IN SILICO EVALUATION

Maja Milanović¹, Nataša Milošević¹, Jovana Drljača¹, Nataša Milić¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3,
Novi Sad, Serbia
maja.milanovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Benzophenones (BPs) are one of the most known classes of UV-filters. The increased production and usage of UV-filters in the last decade consequently led to BPs ubiquitous presence in the environment and continuous human exposure. Based on the U.S. National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, BP-3 is omnipresent xenobiotic in the urine of the general population. BP-3 and its metabolite BP-1 are commonly used in personal care products as UV-filters and stabilizers. Considering the potential estrogenic properties, due to the similar structure with oestrogen, different countries urged for additional toxicological studies in order to review the safety of BPs. The aim of this study was to evaluate the binding potential of BPs for androgen receptor. A set of BPs: BP, BP-1, BP-2, BP-3, BP-4, BP-6, BP-7, BP-8, BP-9, BP-10, BP-12, 4-OH-BP, 4-Me-BP, and 2,3,4-OH-BP was tested as potential ligands for androgen receptor using Genetic Optimisation for Ligand Docking (GOLD, version 2020.3.0). Crystal structure of the androgen receptor (PDB entry code 4K7A) ligand binding domain in complex with minoxidil was used. Binding affinities of the analyzed BPs, expressed as ChemPLP fitness scores, were in the range 46.3-71.7 (minoxidil affinity-73.8). The highest score was obtained for BP-12, while BP showed the lowest ChemPLP value. The obtained fitness scores for BP-3 and BP-1 were 50.2 and 54.2, respectively. Further studies that integrate in silico methods with in vitro assays and in vivo animal models are necessary in order to understand potential consequences of exposure to BPs, especially during pregnancy.

Key words: *endocrine disruptors; molecular docking; personal care products; sunscreen creams*

Acknowledgement: *This work was supported by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, AP Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia [grant number 142-451- 3120/2022-01]*